

Assessment of E-Library Space and Facilities: From the Perspective of the University Librarians

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Abstract:- An E-library is an electronic or online library where one can access books, journals, novels, articles, or any other information over the net. Library planners must acknowledge that the availability of space (or lack of it) is not the sole reason for examining physical facilities. If your library emphasizes current material and best sellers and encourages browsing use of the collection, fewer seats are needed, and the projection should be adjusted downward. If your library emphasizes research material and encourages long-term use by students and scholars, additional seats may be needed, and the projection should be adjusted upward. The study aims to assess the space and facilities of the newly constructed E-library of the University on Main Campus from the perspective of the university librarians. A survey research method using the combination of ocular inspections of the e-library and survey questionnaire was adopted for the study to adequately assess the opinion of the university librarians at Bulacan State University. Findings show that 81% of the respondents strongly agreed with the building's state-of-the-art character. 64% of the respondents strongly agree that the E-library creates a sense of arrival. It is welcoming and has an accommodating atmosphere, and there is enough staff work area and enough available collection spaces. 54.54% of the respondents agreed that the E-library has the projection of service population for the next 20 years.

Keywords:- *E-library, state of the art, assessment, librarians, space, facilities.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Since it was established, Bulacan State University has had decentralized libraries for a long time. In its pursuit of offering a more responsive, state-of-the-art library, the administration invested in infrastructure development, and one of these is the E-library. An E-library is an electronic or online library where one can access books, journals, novels, articles, or any other information over the net. A general reader or a research scholar may have access to several e-libraries sitting at home. An e-library or Digital library is a physical site and/ or website that provide around-the-clock online access to digitized audio, video, and written material. It offers access to electronic resources, printed books, journals, etc., available to the users.

Library planners must acknowledge that the availability of space (or lack of it) is not the sole reason for examining physical facilities. Energy efficiency and condition of the heating, ventilating and air conditioning systems (ideal temperature and humidity for preserving materials are 65 to 70o with 35 to 50% humidity), adaptability to meet the electrical and telecommunications requirements of tomorrow's library technologies, assessment of the general effectiveness of work flow, accessibility to people with disabilities, and compliance with federal, state and local fire, safety, and building codes are all suitable reasons to examine the structure that houses your local library (Library Space Planning Guide, 2002).

Since library buildings are a significant capital investment for most universities, they must be planned to respond to current and future needs. The projected service population is used to calculate several of the categories of library space that follow. By projecting the library's collection size, the space needed to house the collection can be quantified. It is most effective to make these projections over a 20-year period. Changing technology makes it difficult to plan this space; however, there will be a demand that all public and staff areas of the library provide for the connection of computers and information appliances, both mobile and fixed, that use two-way voice, data and/or video communications services.

Technology plays significant role in the building system. Technology is fast evolving and continuously improving and developing almost everyday to be able to become responsive to the needs of the human convenience, safety, accuracy, and fast access in terms of communication and information.

Universities in the Philippines nowadays as Educational Institution has continuously improved as it turned its conventional, traditional set up into state-of-the-art facilities to cater the ever-changing need of the students, faculty, personnel, researchers, and community. State Universities as government funded institution are not behind other private university in terms of infrastructure development. Clear and concrete example is the Bulacan State University, significant and remarkable physical campus improvement took place under the leadership of Dr. Cecilia N. Gascon and one of her iconic projects is the construction of the multi-level E-library located in the main campus of Bulacan State University. The E-library is well-designed facilities that encapsulated the modern library

equipped with modern appliance and equipment that are accessible and ready to serve its clientele.

E-library plays a key role in the learning process of the students. The more accessible and the more complete the services the library can provide, the better result in can give to its clientele. State University library can now view as competitive not just because of its quality teaching but because of its facilities ready to accept the challenges of the globalizing education.

• Objective of the Study

The study aims to assess the space and facilities of the newly constructed E-library in Bulacan State University, Main Campus in the perspective of the university librarians.

II. METHODOLOGY

Survey research method using the combination of ocular inspections of the e-library and survey questionnaires developed and used for the study to assess the opinion of the university librarians in Bulacan State University. The target population of the study comprises the entire staff and librarians having Part-time, Employment by Job Order, Contract of Services and Permanent in status of the University.

III. RESULTS, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

A. Background of Information of the Bulacan State University Library

To support the mission of the university, the library promotes information literacy and provides wide variety of print and non-print materials, other learning resources and services. To enhance the curriculum a wide variety of print and non-print materials supporting cultural and recreational needs of the individuals and the community. The use of bibliographic instruction for efficient and accurate use of information resources. Promotion of learning and implementation of changing technology through its staff, facility, equipment, and programs.

Mission (Source: <https://bulsu.edu.ph/library/>)

The Bulacan State University library is a hospitable place with expert staff assistance, systematic programs, to exchange ideas, promotes literacy, cultural enrichment, and a sense of community.

a) Goals (Source: <https://bulsu.edu.ph/library/>)

- Promote development of literacy among students as educational and reading center for the academic community, developing collection of high-quality materials and a schedule of programs stimulating learning and thinking.
- Center for access to technology and navigate knowledge, promote patrons' information literacy by helping them sift and evaluate information from various sources. Maintaining an up-to-date, reliable computer network with access to useful software.
- Destination for stakeholders offering a relevant collection of library materials, a pleasant place to

meet friends and an impressive schedule of programs and activities.

- Encourage students, faculty, and staff to use library resources to further their academic pursuits.
- Strive to continuously improve service for the library clientele.
- Regularly review the goals of Bulacan State University library and, if necessary, revise them based on current demand and need. (Source: <https://bulsu.edu.ph/library/>)

b) Objectives (Source: <https://bulsu.edu.ph/library/>)

- To provide educational and instructional materials responsive to the needs of Bulacan State University community.
- To conduct timely and appropriate library instruction for both student and faculty.
- To encourage the students, faculty, and personnel on how to use the Online Public Access Catalog.
- To acquire books and other library materials through purchase, gifts and exchange, or donation in line with the demand of the curricular programs of the University.
- To establish linkages / networking / resource sharing with partner institutions and organizations.

c) Services Offered (Source: <https://bulsu.edu.ph/library/>)

- Automated Circulation
- Book Display
- Current Awareness Services (CAS)
- Database Searching
- Information and Referral Services (I & R)
- Internet Access
- Library Orientation
- Library Tour
- Reference Service
- Web On-Line Public Access Catalog (OPAC)
- Wi-Fi Network

B. Bulacan State University E-Library state of the art facilities

Fig. 1: Bulacan State University Main Campus E-library.

Fig. 2: The Lobby of the E-library, Bulacan State University, Main Campus

Fig. 3: E-library maximized the natural light.

Fig. 4: The E-library function and conference room

Fig. 5: The E-library reading area

Fig. 6: E-library's one of the state-of-the-art facilities

Fig. 7: The E-library auditorium

Fig. 8: E-library semi-circular conference room

Fig. 9: E-library audio-visual room

Fig. 10: E-library study area

C. Findings of the survey from University Librarians

Chart 1: Employment Status of the University Librarians currently employed (S.Y. 2021-2022)

50% of the respondents are Contract of Service in their employment status. None of the respondents are Employment by Job Order and Part-time.

Chart 2: Participation in conceptualization of the E-library

50% of the respondents agreed that they got involvement during the conceptualization of the E-Library, or they have participation. 2 out of 22 respondents expressed that they were not involved.

Chart 3: Conducted stakeholders meeting for the construction of E-Library

50% of the respondents strongly agreed that there are stakeholders meeting conducted for the construction of E-Library. Only one respondent strongly disagreed that there are stakeholders meeting conducted.

Chart 4: Stakeholders opinion and recommendations taken into consideration

50% of the respondents agreed that their given opinion and recommendations during the stakeholders meeting were considered. While 1 out of 22 respondents strongly disagreed.

Chart 5: Projection of service population for the next 20 years

54.54% of the respondents agreed that the E-library has the projection of service population for the next 20 years. While there is one respondent expressed to strongly disagree.

Chart 6: Sense of arrival

64% of the respondents strongly agree that the E-library create sense of arrival, that it is welcoming and has accommodating atmosphere. While one respondent is undecided.

Chart 7: Natural sunlight

50% of the respondents strongly agreed that the building maximized the use of natural sunlight in its design. While one respondent strongly disagreed.

Chart 8: Spaces for collection

64% of the respondents strongly agreed that the E-Library has enough available collection spaces. While two of the respondents were undecided and strongly disagreed.

Chart 9: Public Electronic Workstation Space and Information on Automation Needs.

50% of the respondents strongly agreed that the E-library is equipped with Public Electronic Workstation Space and Information on Automation Needs.

Chart 10: Seating space

59% of the respondents strongly agreed that the E-library has enough seating space. While one respondent strongly disagreed.

Chart 11: Staff work area

64% of the respondents strongly agreed that there is enough staff work area, while 36% of the respondents strongly agreed.

Chart 12: Meeting room space

68% of the respondents strongly agreed that there is enough meeting room space (Most public libraries provide meeting rooms to accommodate library-sponsored programs and other community meetings). While 32% of the respondents agreed.

Chart 13: Special- Use space

45% of the respondents strongly agreed that there is Special-Use Space (Special-use space provides space for elements of an individual library's program of service or special types of furnishings that have not been accounted for in earlier sections of this outline). While the other 45% of the respondents agreed.

Chart 14: Non-Assignable Space

50% of the respondents agreed that there is provision for non-assignable space in the newly constructed e-library. While one respondent strongly disagreed that there is such provision.

Chart 15: Sufficient building mechanism

64% of the respondents strongly agreed that the e-library is equipped with sufficient building mechanism like elevators and 36% of the respondents agreed in the availability of the building mechanism.

Chart 16: Building Fire Safety

64% of the respondents strongly agreed that the building is equipped with fire safety mechanism like fire suppression apparatus, fire exits doors and stairs, fire detectors, alarms etc. while one respondent strongly disagreed about the building fire safety.

Chart 17: Person with disability friendly

59% of the respondents strongly agreed that the e-library is following compliance with the PWD requirements. One respondent in undecided in his response.

Chart 18: State of the Art facilities

81% of the respondents strongly agreed in the building state of the art character. There are 18% respondents who are agreed on the e-lib state of the art facilities.

IV. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

Bulacan State University constructed its E-library on the main campus, a state-of-the-art multi-level library. The purpose of the library is to promote information literacy while providing a wide variety of print and non-print materials, other learning resources, and services supporting the university's mission. 50% of the respondents agreed that they got involvement during the conceptualization of the E-Library. The building maximized the use of natural. The E-library has the projection of service population for the next 20 years, has enough available collection spaces, is equipped with Public Electronic Workstation Space and Information on Automation Needs, enough staff work area, and provision for non-assignable space. The E-library is equipped with sufficient building mechanisms like elevators, fire safety mechanisms like fire suppression apparatus, fire exits doors and stairs, fire detectors, alarms, etc. At the same time, one respondent strongly disagreed about building fire safety.

V. CONCLUSION

From the librarian's perspective, the Bulacan State University E-library assessment has clearly shown that they are generally satisfied with the way the building is planned. As a government-run and funded university, Bulacan State University has significantly improved its facilities. The newly constructed E-library is one of the states of the art and one of the most responsive buildings on the campus that is energy efficient and has technological advancement. Since library buildings are a significant capital investment for most universities, they must be planned to respond to current and future needs. The projected service population is used to calculate several categories of library space. The space needed to house the collection can be quantified by projecting the library's collection size. It is most effective to make these projections over 20 years. Changing technology

makes it difficult to plan this space; therefore, accurate and well-planned library can only be achieved through participated approach as the stakeholder's opinions are taken into consideration.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

Hence based on the findings of this research, the following are strongly recommended:

- Stakeholders must be consistently involved in any development, change and improvement that will be done in future to make sure that all dimensions are taken into considerations.
- Large windows that promote natural lighting should not be covered with curtains or blinds to maximize the use of natural lights and avoid the use of artificial lights.
- Periodic and strategic monitoring of the computerized, technological, and state or the arts equipment to ensure smooth flow of library services.
- Timely maintenance of the facilities including the fire suppression apparatus, water sprinklers, smoke detectors, fire alarms, exit doors and ladders as well as mechanical equipment like elevators must be conducted.
- Manning of competent professionals and technical staff and personnel to make sure that the operations will be organize as well as proper care of facilities.

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